

Dream islands and island dreams: Hawai‘i and Berlin

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Voyages to the islands of dreams

1: Johann Gottfried Schadow

200 years ago, on October 26, 1824, the Berlin sculptor and draughtsman Johann Gottfried Schadow wrote under one of his drawings: “Harry Sandwich Islands. 26. octob. 1824.” Who was this “Harry” and where are the “Sandwich Islands” actually located? So much can already be revealed: Harry was the first Hawaiian who arrived in Prussia and his home islands are known today as Hawai‘i - not to be confused with Haiti in the Caribbean.

Even today, Kaua‘i, O‘ahu, Maui and Hawai‘i are among the destinations that many people dream of visiting – but they also often say: I've never been to Hawai‘i. Neither the desire to travel today nor easy flight connections bring the archipelago in the middle of the Pacific for Europeans as close as some islands in the Mediterranean or the Canary Islands, the “islands of eternal spring”. This is why dreams of the South Seas in general and the islands of Hawai‘i in particular have played an important role in music, visual art, newspaper articles, radio and television broadcasts and other areas of culture up to the present day. This is shown not only by examples such as the banner “Visa-free to Hawai” [sic] at one of the so-called Monday demonstrations during the peaceful revolution in Leipzig in 1989 or “Dreamboat” episodes on German entertainment television, but also by references to the “dream islands” in pop lyrics and movies.

These imaginary worlds have roots going back more than 200 years. Since the 18th century, tales of the paradise islands in the German literature have reflected dreams of a better world as well as other than spiritual desires. Not only the reports of French and English expeditions, but also the book “Johann Reinhold Forster's Reise um die Welt während den Jahren 1772 bis 1775” by the Prussian naturalist Georg Forster (1754-1794) formed the basis of the ideas of the South Seas. This translation of “A Voyage Round the World” (1777), published in two volumes in 1778 and 1780, was followed shortly afterwards by “Heinrich Zimmermanns von Wissloch in der Pfalz, Reise um die Welt, mit Capitain Cook” (Journey around the world with Captain Cook of Heinrich Zimmermann from Wissloch of the Palatinate, 1781). The British painter John Webber (1751-1793), who was sometimes called Johann Wäber because of his Swiss origins, also took part in Captain Cook's third voyage around the South Seas from 1776 to 1779/1780. The engravings based on his drawings supplemented the texts of the official travel report and remain important historical documents to this day.

Voyages to the islands of dreams

2: John Webber: A man of the Sandwich Islands dancing

In his book *“Hawai‘i and the German speaking peoples, Hawai‘i a me ka po‘e o nā ‘āina Kelemānia”* (1982), Niklaus Schweizer traced the history of island dreams for Germany, Austria and Switzerland, which continued to be dreamed of when cultural contacts increased in the 19th century with international trade and later traveling.

3: Georg Forster
(1754–1794)

4: Heinrich Zimmermann
(1741–1805)

5: Niklaus Schweizer (*1939)

Voyages to the islands of dreams

Niklaus Schweizer was Honorary Consul of Switzerland in Honolulu for many years and taught at the University of Hawai‘i at Mānoa, as did the German scholar Anneliese W. Moore. Born in Tempelhof, she worked as a secretary and interpreter at the U.S. weather station during the Berlin Airlift (1948-1949), where she met the Californian meteorologist, Paul Moore. After the end of the airlift, the two married and moved directly to Honolulu.

But even in faraway Hawai‘i, Anneliese W. Moore remained connected to the German language and literature. She analyzed the files from the “Central State Archives” in Merseburg and published her biography of the first Hawaiian in Prussia, “Harry Maitey: from Polynesia to Prussia”, in the “Hawaiian Journal of History” in 1977.

*6: Anneliese
Wilhelmine Moore*

Thanks to the work of Anneliese W. Moore and Niklaus Schweizer, not only the memory of the travels of such famous people as James Cook was kept alive, but also the exciting life story of Harry Maitey, who came to Prussia as a teenager and found a new home on Peacock Island as an adult.

Dream islands of the South Seas and Prussian trading dreams

7: King Kamehameha I of Hawai'i

Knowledge about the dream islands of the South Seas had already reached German-speaking countries in the last quarter of the 18th century through Georg Forster and Heinrich Zimmermann. The natural scientist and poet Adelbert von Chamisso also came to Hawai'i during the Rurik expedition under the command of Otto von Kotzebue in November 1816 and September 1817. Even before his *Remarks and Opinions of the Naturalist of the Expedition* were printed in Weimar in 1821, his observations had already spread in Berlin and his friend E. T. A. Hoffmann published his epistolary novella "Haimatochare" in Berlin in 1819, the first European work of prose set on the Hawaiian island of O'ahu. Hawai'i was therefore not only no longer terra incognita, but already a literary setting when the "Mentor" set sail from Bremen in December 1822.

As the "Age of Discovery" reached its end, the major trade routes had already shifted to the oceans when Prussia set out to open up new markets with its first circumnavigation of the globe. While the "East India" and "West India" companies of European countries had long since established extensive trade links, the *Royal Prussian Asiatic Company in Emden to Canton and China* had only been founded in ambitious Prussia under King Frederick II. Its ships brought not only tea and spices to the country, but also luxury goods such as porcelain and silk. However, the decline of the company began with the Seven Years' War (1756-1763) and it was finally dissolved in 1765.

8: Sealing mark of the "General Directorate of the Shipping Trade Society"

Just seven years later, the "General Directorate of the Shipping Trade Society" was founded in Berlin, although it was not particularly successful at first – partly due to the Napoleonic Wars. This changed when it became an independent financial and trading institution under state supervision. From 1820 onward, Christian Rother in particular shaped the Shipping Trade Society's ventures, which also included the first Prussian circumnavigation of the world with the "Mentor". However, the merchant frigate was not yet in Prussian hands when it sailed from Bremen, but the Berlin merchant Wilhelm Oswald, who was responsible for the cargo, supervised the trading business as supercargo from the very beginning.

9: The Royal Prussian naval vessel Mentor sailing around Cap Horn

Like the Prussian ships of the Emden East Asian Trading Company, the "Mentor" was also supposed to make port in Canton, China – this time, however, coming from the east. After sailing around Cape Horn and stops in the Chilean ports of Valparaíso and Coquimbo, the ship arrived in the port of Honolulu on the island of O‘ahu in the Kingdom of Hawai‘i on November 28, 1823. The day before, King Liholiho and Queen Kamāmalu, accompanied by Boki, the governor of O‘ahu, his wife Kuini Liliha and other companions, had left Hawai‘i for London on board the British whaler "L'Aigle", although there was "*great stir among the chiefs about the king going to England*", as Stephen Reynolds had already noted in his diary on November 8. Wilhelm Oswald observed immediately after the arrival of the "Mentor" that "*the death of a chief, who was buried in the morning, ... caused deep mourning among all those present*".

10: *Mahiolo*

It is not known whether these political events had anything to do with the fact that a young Hawaiian who introduced himself as “Harry” wanted to be taken on board the “Mentor”. When the ship left Honolulu for Canton on December 3, he saw his homeland Hawai‘i for the last time in his life. Also on board with him were a number of items that had been acquired during his short stay, including a woven helmet (*mahiolo*), which is now on display at the Humboldt Forum in Berlin. The Germans also called Harry “Maitey” and this name, which goes back to the Hawaiian “*maita‘i*”, later became his surname in Prussia. Since the sources always describe Harry Maitey as friendly and gentle, the meanings “good, fine, all right” of “*maita‘i*” probably suited his character.

11: *King Liholiho and Queen Kamāmalu in the theater in London*

No one knows what dreams of the future in a distant land sailed with Harry Maitey to Canton and then on to Europe via Java and St. Helena. At the same time as the “Mentor” was sailing through the English Channel, a ship was preparing to depart from the Thames to return the mortal remains of King Liholiho and Queen Kamāmalu to Hawai‘i, who had been infected with measles and died in London.

The “Mentor” had been purchased by the Prussian Shipping Trade Society during the returning voyage and was therefore ordered to Swinemünde, where it arrived on September 14, 1824. King Frederick William III decided that Christian Rother, the president of the Shipping Trade Society, was to bring Harry Maitey to Berlin and accommodate him. The “Sandwich Islander” now had

his domicile in the “Jägerstraße” on the corner of the “Gendarmenmarkt”. What else would his eyes see in a foreign country – and through what eyes would the Berliners see him?

Island paradise Peacock Island

12: Johann Gottfried Schadow (1764–1850): “Harry of the Sandwich Islands, en face and in profile to the left”

On October 18, 1824, the “Royal Privileged Berlin Newspaper of State and Scholarly Matters” reported on the voyage of the Prussian merchant ship “Mentor” under the heading “Science and art news”:

For an ethnographic museum, the construction of which we are still awaiting, many a curious thing has also come along; we only noticed a light dance dress of the Chileans made of bear guts, stuff made of tree bark from the Sandwich Islands, drinking vessels made of gourds, fans made of peacock feathers, helmets made of rushes, weapons, fishing rods and household utensils of various kinds.

However, the “volunteer from the Sandwich Islands” that the mentor had also brought from Hawai‘i aroused particular interest:

Henry, as he is called, or rather that is what he calls himself, came on board when the mentor docked there and begged to be taken along. They inquired about his family circumstances, he had neither father nor mother, nor anyone else who made claims on him; so he went with them to China, and has now become completely accustomed to the European way of life. Henry may be about 15 to 18 years old, [...] he has tattoos on his arm and face. He is very eager to learn, friendly, lively and hard-working. He speaks German words fluently, if they do not have too many consonants, especially the r seems to be missing completely.

Just eight days later, “Harry of the Sandwich Islands” sat for the Berlin sculptor and draughtsman Johann Gottfried Schadow for a drawing “en face and in profile to the left”. The artist later described how he saw the portrayed person in his “Polyclet”:

To the north of this island, in the line between Mexico and China, lie the Sandwich Islands, from which the ship Mentor brought an inhabitant named Harry, whose portrait, in profile and face, is shown on this plate. Since he

Island paradise Peacock Island

has remained among us, an inspection of his features shows that there is nothing different from ours. The broad cheekbones are also to be found among us, and although his skull is more slender, this is nevertheless concealed by the strong and thick hair; what distinguishes him to some extent is the darker color of his skin. He was not suited to a more refined intellectual education. This shows how great the difference is between the appearance of the islanders of this large expanse of water.

Anyone comparing the two contemporary quotes and the drawing will notice an interesting detail: According to the report in the “Voss’s Newspaper”, Harry Maitey's face was tattooed – but neither the drawing shows the facial adornment nor does the description mention it. Rather, Schadow seems to have been particularly focused on making sure the “facial features do not differ from ours”.

The image shows a handwritten letter on aged paper. The text is written in cursive and is mostly in German. At the bottom left, the date "Berlin, 15. April, 1827." is clearly visible. At the bottom right, there is a signature that appears to be "Humboldt". The handwriting is somewhat slanted and dense.

13: Wilhelm von Humboldt's message to Christian Rother on April 15, 1827

The documents about the “Sandwich Islander” are also characterized by sobriety and describe a not very exotic way of life. Initially, Harry lived in the office building of the Prussian Shipping Trade Society with the family of Christian Rother, the president of the Shipping Trade Society, in the Jägerstraße on the corner of the Gendarmenmarkt. In 1825, he began his schooling at the “Boarding school in front of the Halle Gate”, to which he moved two years later. As he was not satisfied with his progress in German, Rother asked the linguist Wilhelm von Humboldt to give Harry extra tuition. The message with which Humboldt agreed on April 15, 1827 has been preserved:

If Your Excellency would send me your Harry this afternoon at 6 o'clock, I would like to try working with him. If it is not possible today, I will ask for him at the same time next Tuesday. With my best wishes for your journey and your warmest and most respectful friendship,

Humboldt

However, Maitey was not tutored in German, but was asked for words from the Hawaiian language. This resulted in the “*Sandwich Glossary*”, which Humboldt presented at the Berlin Academy of Sciences in 1828. Later, in his studies on the Malayo-Polynesian languages, he cited “*Harres Maitai*” as his most important source for the Hawaiian language.

14: New Church and Royal Theater 1833

The year 1830 marked two important events for the young Harry. On April 30, he was baptized and confirmed in the New Church on Gendarmenmarkt. Although King Friedrich Wilhelm III had spoken out against it, he was given the German first names Heinrich and Wilhelm at his baptism. At the same time, April 30, 1807 was set as the date of his birth on the baptismal certificate. In August, Maitey was taken into the royal household and at the same time assigned as an assistant to the machinery master on Peacock Island.

Associated with this island are imageries such as “Prussian paradise” or “Prussian Arcadia”, as Frederick William III had it equipped with various gardens and had exotic animals gathered there. It is therefore sometimes assumed that the “Sandwich Islander” was also intended to enrich the island paradise as an “exotic”. This overlooks the fact that Maitey only failed to enter court service because of a failed examination. So now – quite unlike paradise – he was trained by machinery master Friedrich as a turner, locksmith and carpenter.

After marrying Dorothea Charlotte Becker, the animal keeper’s daughter, in 1833, the Peacock Island changed from a residential to a working location, as the young couple moved to Klein-Glienicke. It is not known whether it was only due to the longer commute that Maitey was increasingly absent from the island. In any case, it led to tensions with Friedrich, who eventually made an official complaint. Maitey was then assigned to the royal court gardener Fintelmann.

15: Chest portrait (around 1850) in the Brandenburg-Prussian House Archive

For the less than 40 years from his marriage until his death in 1872, official sources about Maitey become increasingly sparse. As the king's "sandwich islander", he was paid by the royal court, but probably offered no reason for greater public attention. The contrast with the "Science and art news" of the "Voss's Newspaper" after the arrival of the tattooed youth in Berlin, whom Schadow portrayed and who provided Wilhelm von Humboldt with Hawaiian language material, is clearly recognizable. But perhaps this only shows that Harry Maitey, to whom the "Voss's Newspaper" had certified in 1824 that he had "*become completely accustomed to the European way of life*", simply led a completely normal life on the island paradise of Peacock Island and in Klein-Glienicke?

Fading dreams and new recollections

Dreams and reality are usually seen as opposites. However, a closer look reveals that our own ideas, preconceptions and dreams also influence our perception of reality. The more distant things, processes and people are from us in space or time, the more difficult it becomes to distinguish facts from ideas.

16: Hula noho

When Harry Maitey, as the first Hawaiian, arrived in Prussia, ideas of the paradise-like South Sea Islands had already been formed by the descriptions of voyages to previously unknown parts of the world. However, these reports were never able to paint a detailed overall picture and were also influenced by the views of the people giving them. Now the “Mentor”, returning from her circumnavigation of the globe, not only brought “*stuff made from tree bark [...], drinking vessels made from gourds*” and “*helmets made from reeds*” from Hawai‘i to Berlin, but also a “Sandwich Islander” in person, who had “*already become completely accustomed to the European way of life*”. In the “Voss’s Newspaper” of October 18, 1824, it was also reported what an impression this young man made when he was invited to sing:

“When he sang, he sat on a chair and made lively movements with his hands, and it seemed remarkable to me that he often struck his heart with his right hand, while he never touched his right side with his left. His singing was limited to only four or five notes, and the words seemed to consist mainly of the sounds ae, i and o, his voice has nothing buzzing about it, one could call it a pleasant tenor voice, but the performance of the singing with these strange movements made quite the impression of seeing a madman.”

This description shows that Harry Maitey introduced the Berlin audience to a hula that was danced sitting down (*bula noho*), because the described movements of the hands follow the rules for performing the hula that are still applied today.

17: "Acta concerning the Sandwich Islander Harry Maitey brought in by the sea trading vessel Mentor"

What image of the distant islands could interested Berliners draw from all this? Although the report quoted in the "Voss's Newspaper" of October 18, 1824 and the surviving documents in the files of the "Prussian Shipping Trade Society" and the "Royal Civil Cabinet" describe some details such as the expenses for shoemakers or a report from the director of the "Boarding School in front of the Halle Gate" that Maitey's progress in German and religion was "not the most brilliant", they hardly allow any conclusions to be drawn about the young man's daily life.

The two drawings made by Johann Gottfried Schadow in October 1824 give us an idea of Maitey's appearance. But it is not known why he omitted the tattoo on the young Hawaiian's face. Was his interest in physiognomy the reason or was there another intention behind it, as described by the artist Guillaume Bruère?

"Unlike many of his predecessors and contemporaries, Schadow was not driven by exoticism, but by a deeply humanistic approach to understanding and conveying the foreign as an enrichment and a sign of diversity and abundance."

Even beyond the "sandwich word list" compiled by Wilhelm von Humboldt, we have no information about what the linguist and Harry Maitey discussed. Was the retrieval of Hawaiian words Humboldt's way of helping the young man to continue learning German – as the President of the Prussian Shipping Trade Society, Christian Rother, had expected him to do? Or was Humboldt simply taking the opportunity to gain some research material at first hand?

18: Feather cloak ('ahu 'ula) of King Kamehameha I.

It is to the great credit of Anneliese W. Moore that she has meticulously analyzed the files on the “Sandwich Islander”. At the same time, these files offer few clues for describing Harry Maitey as a person and his character. Moore’s biographical essay “*Harry Maitey: From Polynesia to Prussia*” therefore also shows in an impressive way how the intercultural experiences of her life in Hawai‘i enabled her to get closer to Maitey as a person. One example of this is her interpretation that the young Harry understood the relationship with Christian Rother as a typical adoption (*bānai*) in Hawai‘i. However, it remains questionable whether this transfer to other events on record can stand up to closer examination. Moore attributes the incident described in the files, in which Maitey had behaved inappropriately in Rother’s opinion and for which he was to be punished, to an unexpected confrontation between Maitey and the feather cloak (*‘ahu ‘ula*) of Kamehameha I on display at the Prussian Shipping Trade Society. It was a gift from King Kamehameha III Kauikeaouli to Frederick William III and arrived in Hamburg on the Princess Louise in 1829, before traveling on to Berlin. However, there is no mention of the feather cloak in the records at the passage cited by Anneliese W. Moore.

19: King David Kalākaua, painting in the Blue Salon of the 'Iolani Palace (William F. Cogswell)

Also, the question as to why Harry Maitey did not take advantage of the opportunities to return to his homeland with the “Princess Louise” in 1825 and 1830, but remained in Prussia and finally started a family with Dorothea Charlotte Becker, cannot be answered on the basis of the files. His life on the Pfaueninsel and later in Klein-Glienicke probably went unnoticed in Berlin outside the court bureaucracy. He is not mentioned in the newspapers on the occasion of King Kalākaua's visit in 1881 and it is also not known whether his widow and his son Heinrich Wilhelm Eduard met the Hawaiian king.

However, the “Sandwich Islander” had not only disappeared from public memory by the end of the 19th century. Even Johann Friedrich Meuß, who consulted the archives for his article in the “Hohenzollern Yearbook” 1912 on the “Relations of King Frederick William III and King Frederick William IV with Kamehameha III of Hawaii”, was mistaken in his assumption:

“Since the records do not contain any royal provisions about the Hawaiian, it can be assumed that he returned to his homeland on the sea trading ship “Princess Louise”, which was sent on the same voyage in 1825.”

Oral traditions about Maitey's origins or his original name “*Kaparena*” appeared in magazine articles written by Caesar von der Ahé in the early 1930s. Some of these go back to Eduard Maitey, who died in 1906, and cannot be confirmed by other sources.

Half a century later, Niklaus R. Schweizer not only made Anneliese W. Moore's study known in the German-speaking world, but also placed the story of the first Hawaiian in a larger cultural-historical framework in his publication “*Hawai'i and the German speaking peoples*”. Like Anneliese

W. Moore, he not only taught for many years at the University of Hawai‘i in Mānoa, but also studied the Hawaiian language and culture.

In Berlin and Brandenburg, Michael Seiler, Director of Horticulture at the Prussian Palaces and Gardens Foundation, ensured that Harry Maitey was not forgotten. When he gave a lecture on the first Hawaiian in Prussia in the Checkpoint Charlie Foundation’s series “Transatlantic Travelers – Extraordinary Transatlantic Lives from the 18th to 21st Centuries” at the “European Academy Berlin” on June 10, 2008, the program also included a performance of Hawaiian hula by the group “*No Ka Ho‘omana‘o Ana Ia Berlin*” (In Memory of Berlin). Michael Seiler remarked afterwards: “*Now I understand this description in the ‘Voss’s Newspaper’*”. He thus encouraged some members of the group to take a closer look at this extraordinary life story that spanned Hawai‘i and Berlin.

20: *Hula kahiko, Hālau o Kekuhi at the Merrie Monarch Festival in Hilo, Hawai‘i*

Hawaiian hula uses chants, hand gestures and body movements to tell stories that have been passed down over many generations. It is therefore Hawai‘i’s most important cultural heritage and, together with the Hawaiian language, has been revitalized since the 1970s in the “*Hawaiian Renaissance*”, not only in today’s US state. With the support of Hawaiian teachers (*kumu hula*), hula schools (*halau hula*) have also been established in Californian cities, Japan and Europe. In spring 2012, Kumu Frank Ka‘ananā Akima visited “*No Ka Ho‘omana‘o Ana Ia Berlin*” for the first time and was guided by members of the group to Harry Maitey’s grave at Nikolskoe Cemetery.

Since in Hawai‘i new hula are emerging alongside the preservation of the traditional repertoire of ancient dances, the group already had the idea of honoring Harry Maitey with a so-called name song (*mele inoa*). After the visit at the grave Frank Ka‘ananā Akima was deeply moved and requested to describe Maitey as a person and the outstanding events of his life. Aki Dinda and Hapi Hermann took this description with them when they visited Honolulu in the spring of 2013 and, together with Kumu Ka‘ananā, first wrote the English lyrics of a song in honor of the first Hawaiian who came to Berlin on April 15, 1813. Leimomi Akana and Kiele Gonzalez then translated the text into Hawaiian. The composition of the chant in traditional style (*kahiko*) and the choreography were provided by Kumu Ka‘ananā.

21: Honolulu harbor around 1827

“*He mele no Harry Maitey*” (A song in honor of Harry Maitey) was first publicly performed in 2015 by “*No Ka Ho ‘omana ‘o Ana Ia Berlin*” in the presence of Kumu Frank Ka‘ananā Akima at the Tempelhof Field. The first verse describes the journey from Honolulu to Prussia and is repeated after the fourth verse:

E ‘e i ka moku e ‘ike i ke ao ...

Board this ship to see the world ...

Liholibo and Kamāmalu have already started the journey before ...

What will his eyes see?

In the second verse, Harry Maitey is described as a young man presenting songs from his homeland:

He keiki ‘olu‘olu ...

*A gentle child from the Sandwich Islands, an inquisitive child,
he tells the knowledge of his country in song,
his heart trembles and is filled with love.*

22: Nēnē

Maitey not only spent many years on Peacock Island, but was also reminded of his homeland in the summer of 1834 when the “*Princess Louise*” brought back Hawaiian geese from her third circumnavigation of the world:

'O Peacock Island ...

*The Peacock Island is a pearl among the summer residences of the Prussian nobility,
a home surrounded by fragrant flowers and plants from foreign lands,
the trees shade proud peacocks and rare Nēnē geese,
a gift from the homeland of the man from the Sandwich Islands.*

23: Harry Maitey's grave: Inscription for himself and his wife

In the fourth verse, the inscription on the grave is quoted and the memories of him are described:

Pa'a 'ia ma ka pōbaku ilina ...

The gravestone bears the inscription:

*"Here rests under the protection of God the man from the Sandwich Islands, Maitey",
a gentle man from the islands he sang about.*

His path was followed in Prussia and his experiences were understood.

The last sentence is a reference to the Hawaiian Jony Kahopimeai, who was also accommodated for a few months in the "Boarding School in front of the Halle Gate", and also honors him as an important conversation partner of Wilhelm von Humboldt.

With "*He mele no Harry Maitey*", in addition to the various traces that the life of this Hawaiian left behind in documents and other written records, there is a tribute to him with the poetic means of Hawaiian and through the expression of the traditional language of hula. The process of cultural appropriation of his history with the help of linguistic exchange between people in Hawai'i and Germany is complemented by a shared understanding in which new trans-cultural forms emerge from cultural experiences and different methods of dealing with cultural heritage. For the performance of "*He mele no Harry Maitey*", for example, a song and a chant were selected to complement the hula, referring to the cultural exchange with Hawai'i and the "*Hawaiian Renaissance*".

The hymn "*Ho'onani I Ka Makua Man*" is sung to a melody that goes back to the 16th century Genevan Psalter and is known in the English-speaking world as "*Old Hundred*". In Berlin, it has been recorded in hymnals since the 16th century. The text is a translation of a verse of the hymn "*Praise God from whom all blessings flow*" and was written by the missionary Hiram Bingham. After the traditional kapu system and religion were largely abolished in 1819 under the young King Liholiho initiated by his mother Keōpūolani and the regent Ka'ahumanu, the spread and mostly voluntary adoption of Christianity among the Hawaiians began with the arrival of missionaries in

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1820. With the Hawaiian written language for the propagation of the Bible and Hawaiian hymns, the missionaries simultaneously established a foundation for the preservation of the language alongside the oral tradition. With the beginning of the “*Hawaiian Renaissance*”, these written resources could also be used for the revival of the Hawaiian language and culture. In the process, new chants were created, such as the song “*E hō mai*”, written by Edith Kanaka‘ole, which is used to ask for insight and knowledge at the start of an activity. In the performance of “*He mele no Harry Maitey*”, it serves as a song that is not danced to (*oli*).

Just as dreams and imaginations form entire stories from individual details of memory and incomplete information, “*He mele no Harry Maitey*” offers a poetic image of the man from Hawai‘i – “*ke kanaka Sandwich Islands*”, as the song says. His life in Berlin, on Peacock Island and in Klein-Glienicke has left traces that for some are associated with dream islands and island dreams ... for others they provide understanding (*‘ike*) for this life of the first Hawaiian in Prussia.

Appendix

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„Their Majesties King Rheo Rhio (Libolibo), Queen Tamehamalu (Tamamalu), Madame Poke (Boki) of the Sandwich Islands“ by John William Gear (Ausschnitt), 1824, color lithograph, Honolulu Museum of Art accession 9990, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons, https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Their_Majesties_King_Rheo_Rhio,_Queen_Tamehamalu,_Madame_Poke.jpg
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